

Slav-NER: the 3rd Cross-lingual Challenge on Recognition, Normalization, Classification, and Linking of Named Entities across Slavic languages

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Abstract

This paper describes Slav-NER: the 3rd Multilingual Named Entity Challenge in Slavic languages. The tasks involve recognizing mentions of named entities in Web documents, normalization of the names, and cross-lingual linking. The Challenge covers six languages and five entity types, and is organized as part of the 8th Balto-Slavic Natural Language Processing Workshop, co-located with the EACL 2021 Conference. Ten teams participated in the competition. Performance for the named entity recognition task reached 90% F-measure, much higher than reported in the first edition of the Challenge. Seven teams covered all six languages. Detailed evaluation information is available on the shared task web page.

1 Introduction

Analyzing named entities (NEs) in Slavic languages poses a challenging problem, due to the rich inflection and derivation, free word order, and other morphological and syntactic phenomena exhibited in these languages (Przepiórkowski, 2007; Piskorski et al., 2009). Encouraging research on detection and normalization of NEs—and on the closely related problem of cross-lingual, cross-document *entity linking*—is of paramount importance for improving multilingual and cross-lingual information access in these languages.

This paper describes the 3rd Shared Task on multilingual NE recognition (NER), which aims at addressing these problems in a systematic way.

The shared task was organized in the context of the 8th BSNLP: Balto-Slavic Natural Language Processing Workshop, co-located with the EACL 2021 conference. The task covers six languages—Bulgarian, Czech, Polish, Russian, Slovene and Ukrainian—and five types of NE: person, location, organization, product, and event. The input text collection consists of documents collected from the Web, each collection centered on a certain “focal” event. The rationale of such a setup is to foster the development of “end-to-end” NER and cross-lingual entity linking solutions, which are not tailored to specific, narrow domains. This paper also serves as an introduction and a guide for researchers wishing to explore these problems using the training and test data, which are released to the public.¹

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews prior work. Section 3 describes the task; Section 4 describes the annotation of the dataset. The evaluation methodology is introduced in Section 5. Participant systems are described in Section 6, and the results obtained by these systems are presented in Section 7. We present the conclusions and lessons learned in Section 8.

2 Prior Work

The work described here builds on the 1st and 2nd Shared Task on Multilingual Named Entity Recognition, Normalization and cross-lingual Match-

¹bsnlp.cs.helsinki.fi/shared_task.html

ing for Slavic Languages, (Piskorski et al., 2017, 2019), which, to the best of our knowledge, are the first attempts at such shared tasks covering multiple Slavic languages.

High-quality recognition and analysis of NEs is an essential step not only for information access, such as document retrieval and clustering, but it also constitutes a fundamental processing step in a wide range of NLP pipelines built for higher-level analysis of text, such as Information Extraction, see, e.g. (Huttunen et al., 2002). Other NER-related shared tasks have been organized previously. The first *non-English* monolingual NER evaluations—covering Chinese, Japanese, Spanish, and Arabic—were held in the context of the Message Understanding Conferences (MUCs) (Chinchor, 1998) and the ACE Programme (Doddington et al., 2004). The first *multilingual* NER shared task, which covered several European languages, including Spanish, German, and Dutch, was organized in the context of the CoNLL conferences (Tjong Kim Sang, 2002; Tjong Kim Sang and De Meulder, 2003). The NE types covered in these campaigns were similar to the NE types covered in our Challenge. Worth mentioning in this context is Entity Discovery and Linking (EDL) (Ji et al., 2014, 2015), a track of the NIST Text Analysis Conferences (TAC). EDL aimed to extract entity mentions from a collection of documents in multiple languages (English, Chinese, and Spanish), and to partition the entities into cross-document equivalence classes, by either linking mentions to a knowledge base or directly clustering them. An important difference between EDL and our task is that EDL required linking entities to a pre-existing knowledge base.

Related to cross-lingual NE recognition is NE transliteration, i.e., linking NEs across languages that use different scripts. A series of NE Transliteration Shared Tasks were organized as a part of NEWS—Named Entity Workshops—(Duan et al., 2016), focusing mostly on Indian and Asian languages. In 2010, the NEWS Workshop included a shared task on Transliteration Mining (Kumaran et al., 2010), i.e., mining of names from parallel corpora. This task included corpora in English, Chinese, Tamil, Russian, and Arabic.

Research on NE focusing on Slavic languages includes tools for NE recognition for Croatian (Karan et al., 2013; Ljubešić et al., 2013), NE recognition in Croatian tweets (Baksa et al., 2017),

a manually annotated NE corpus for Croatian (Agić and Ljubešić, 2014), tools for NE recognition in Slovene (Štajner et al., 2013; Ljubešić et al., 2013), a Czech corpus of 11K annotated NEs (Ševčíková et al., 2007), NER tools for Czech (Konkol and Konopík, 2013), tools and resources for fine-grained annotation of NEs in the National Corpus of Polish (Waszczuk et al., 2010; Savary and Piskorski, 2011), NER shared tasks for Polish organized under the umbrella of POLEVAL² evaluation campaigns (Ogrodniczuk and Łukasz Kobyliński, 2018, 2020). and a recent shared task on NE Recognition in Russian (Starostin et al., 2016).

3 Task Description

The data for this edition of the shared task consists of sets of documents in six Slavic languages: Bulgarian, Czech, Polish, Russian, Slovene and Ukrainian. To accommodate entity linking, each set of documents is chosen to revolve around one certain entity—e.g., a person, an organization or an event. The documents were obtained from the Web, by posing a keyword query to a search engine or publicly available crawled data repositories, and extracting the textual content from the respective sources.

The task is to recognize, classify, and “normalize” all named-entity mentions in each of the documents, and to link across languages all named mentions referring to the same real-world entity. Formally, the Multilingual Named Entity Recognition task is subdivided into three sub-tasks:

- **Named Entity Mention Detection and Classification:** Recognizing all named mentions of entities of five types: persons (PER), organizations (ORG), locations (LOC), products (PRO), and events (EVT).
- **Name Normalization:** Mapping each named mention of an entity to its corresponding *base form*. By “base form” we generally mean the lemma (“dictionary form”) of the inflected word-form. In some cases normalization should go beyond inflection and transform a derived word into a base word’s lemma, e.g., in case of personal possessives (see below). Multi-word names should be normalized to the *canonical multi-word expression*—rather than a sequence

²<http://poleval.pl>

of lemmas of the words making up the multi-word expression.

- **Entity Linking.** Assigning a unique identifier (ID) to each detected named mention of an entity, in such a way that mentions referring to the same real-world entity should be assigned the same ID—referred to as the cross-lingual ID.

The task does not require positional information of the name entity mentions. Thus, for all occurrences of the same form of a NE mention (e.g., an inflected variant, an acronym or abbreviation) within a given document, no more than one annotation should be produced.³ Furthermore, distinguishing typographical case is not necessary since the evaluation is case-insensitive. If the text includes lowercase, uppercase or mixed-case variants of the same entity, the system should produce only one annotation for all of these mentions. For instance, for “*ISIS*” and “*isis*” (provided that they refer to the same NE type), only one annotation should be produced. The recognition of common-noun or pronominal references to named entities does not constitute part of the task.

3.1 Named Entity Classes

The task defines the following five NE classes.

Person names (PER): Names of real (or fictional) persons). Person names should not include titles, honorifics, and functions/positions. For example, in the text fragment “... *President Vladimir Putin*...”, only “*Vladimir Putin*” is recognized as a person name. Both initials and pseudonyms are also considered named mentions of persons. Similarly, toponym-based named references to groups of people (that do not have a formal organization unifying them) should also be recognized, e.g., “*Germans*.” In this context, mentions of a single member belonging to such groups, e.g., “*German*,” should be assigned the same cross-lingual ID as plural mentions, i.e., “*Germans*” and “*German*” when referring to the nation receive the same cross-lingual ID.

Named mentions of other groups of people that do have a formal organization unifying them should be tagged as PER, e.g., in the phrase “*Spart’ané vyhráli*” (Spartans won), “*Spart’ané* are to be tagged as PER.

³Unless the different occurrences have different entity types (different *readings*) assigned to them, which is rare.

Personal possessives derived from a person’s name should be classified as a Person, and the base form of the corresponding name should be extracted. For instance, in “*Trumpov tweet*” (Croatian) one is expected to classify “*Trumpov*” as PER, with the base form “*Trump*.”

Locations (LOC): All toponyms and geopolitical entities—cities, counties, provinces, countries, regions, bodies of water, land formations, etc.—including named mentions of *facilities*—e.g., stadiums, parks, museums, theaters, hotels, hospitals, transportation hubs, churches, streets, railroads, bridges, and similar facilities.

In case named mentions of facilities *also* refer to an organization, the LOC tag should be used. For example, from the text “*San Rafaelle Hospital hired new staff due to Covid-19 pandemic*” the mention “*San Rafaelle Hospital*” should be classified as LOC.

Organizations (ORG): All organizations, including companies, public institutions, political parties, international organizations, religious organizations, sport organizations, educational and research institutions, etc.

Organization designators and potential mentions of the seat of the organization are considered to be part of the organization name. For instance, from the text “...*Zakład Ubezpieczeń Społecznych w Bydgoszczy*...” (The Social Insurance Institution in Bydgoszcz), the full phrase “*Zakład Ubezpieczeń Społecznych w Bydgoszczy*” should be extracted.

Products (PRO): All names of *products and services*, such as electronics (“*Samsung Galaxy A41*”), cars (“*Honda Pilot*”), newspapers (“*Der Spiegel*”), web-services (“*Pintertest*”), medicines (“*Oxycodone*”), awards (“*Pulitzer Prize*”), books (“*Animal Farm*”), TV programmes (“*Wiadomości TVP*”), etc.

When a company name is used to refer to a *service*, e.g., “*na Instagramie*” (Polish for “on Instagram”), the mention of “*Instagramie*” is considered to refer to a service/product and should be tagged as PRO. However, when a company name refers to a service, expressing an opinion of the company, it should be tagged as ORG.

This category also includes legal documents and treaties, e.g., “*Układ z Schengen*” (Pol-

Figure 1: Screenshot of the Inforex Web interface, the tool used for data annotation.

Jacob Serrano (23) z americké Floridy se stal vůbec prvním Američanem, který byl očkován experimentální vakcínou proti koronaviru, ta vznikla za spolupráce vědců z Oxfordské univerzity a farmaceutické společnosti AstraZeneca. Podle WHO jde zatím o nejslibnější očkovací látku. Serrano se neváhal zapojit se do boje s koronavirem, který způsobuje nemoc covid-19, nákaza ho totiž připravila o 7 příbuzných, uvedl list Daily Mail.

114	Američan	Američan	PER	GPE-USA
	AstraZeneca	AstraZeneca	ORG	ORG-AstraZeneca
	Daily Mail	Daily Mail	PRO	PRO-Daily-Mail
	Florida	Florida	LOC	GPE-Florida
	Jacob Serrano	Jacob Serrano	PER	PER-Jacob-Serrano
	Oxfordské univerzity	Oxfordská univerzita	ORG	ORG-University-of-Oxford
	Serrano	Serrano	PER	PER-Jacob-Serrano
	WHO	WHO	ORG	ORG-World-Health-Org
	covid-19	covid-19	EVT	EVT-Covid-19
	koronavirem	koronavirus	EVT	EVT-Covid-19
	koronaviru	koronavirus	EVT	EVT-Covid-19

Figure 2: Example input and output formats.

ish: “Schengen Agreement”) and initiatives, e.g., “Horizon 2020”.

Events (EVT): This category covers named mentions of events, including conferences, e.g. “24. Konference Žárovného Zinkování” (Czech: “Hot Galvanizing Conference”), concerts, festivals, holidays, e.g., “Święta Bożego Narodzenia” (Polish: “Christmas”), wars, battles, disasters, e.g., “Katastrofa Smoleńska” (Polish: “the Smoleńsk air disaster”), outbreaks of infectious diseases (“Spanish Flu”). Future, speculative, and fictive events—e.g., “Polexit”—are considered event mentions too.

3.2 Complex and Ambiguous Entities

In case of complex named entities, consisting of nested named entities, only the *top-most* entity should be recognized. For example, from the text “Università Commerciale Luigi Bocconi” one should not extract “Luigi Bocconi”, but only the top-level entity.

In case one word-form (e.g., “Georgia”) is used to refer to more than one different real-world entities in different contexts in the same document (e.g., a person and a location), two annotations should be returned, associated with different cross-lingual IDs.

In case of coordinated phrases, like “European and German Parliament,” two names should be extracted (as ORG). The lemmas would be “European” and “German Parliament”, and the IDs should refer to “European Parliament” and “German Parliament” respectively.

In rare cases, plural forms might have two annotations—e.g., in the phrase “a border between Irelands”—“Irelands” should be extracted twice with identical lemmas but different IDs.

3.3 System Input and Response

Input Document Format: Documents in the collection are represented in the following format. The first five lines contain the following meta-data (in the respective order): <DOCUMENT-ID>,

<LANGUAGE>, <CREATION-DATE>, <URL>, <TITLE>, <TEXT>. The text to be processed begins from the sixth line and runs till the end of file. The <URL> field stores the origin from which the text document was retrieved. The values of <CREATION-DATE> and <TITLE> were not provided for all documents, due to unavailability of such data or due to errors in parsing during data collection.

System Response. For each input file, the system should return one output file as follows. The first line should contain only the <DOCUMENT-ID>, which corresponds to the input. Each subsequent line contains one annotation, as tab-separated fields:

```
<MENTION> TAB <BASE> TAB <CAT> TAB <ID>
```

The <MENTION> field should be the NE as it appears in text. The <BASE> field should be the base form of the entity. The <CAT> field stores the category of the entity (ORG, PER, LOC, PRO, or EVT) and <ID> is the cross-lingual identifier. The cross-lingual identifiers may consist of an arbitrary sequence of alphanumeric characters. An example document in Czech and the corresponding response is shown in Figure 2.

The detailed descriptions of the tasks are available on the web page of the Shared Task.⁴

4 Data

For Russian, Polish, Czech and Bulgarian, the training and test data sets from the 2019 Shared Task were used as training data for 2021. For the new languages—Ukrainian and Slovene—new training sets were annotated. The test data in all six languages covered two major current topics: the COVID-19 pandemic and the 2020 USA Presidential elections (USA 2020 ELECTIONS).

The 2019 training data consist of four sets of documents extracted from the Web, each related to a given *focus* entity. We tried to choose entities related to events in 2018 and 2019 covered in mainstream news in many languages. ASIA BIBI, which relates to a Pakistani woman involved in a blasphemy case, BREXIT, RYANAIR, which faced a massive strike, and NORD STREAM, a controversial Russian-European project.

Each dataset was created as follows. For the focus entity, we posed a search query to Google

⁴http://bsnlp.cs.helsinki.fi/System_response_guidelines-1.2.pdf

and/or publicly available crawled data repositories, in each of the target languages. The query returned documents in the target language. We removed duplicates, downloaded the HTML—mainly news articles—and converted them into plain text. Since the result of HTML parsing may include not only the main text of a Web page, but also spurious text, some additional manual cleaning was applied whenever necessary. The resulting set of “cleaned” documents were used to manually select documents for each language and topic, for the final datasets.

Documents were annotated using the Inforex⁵ web-based system for annotation of text corpora (Marcinić et al., 2017). Inforex allows parallel access and resource sharing by multiple annotators. It let us share a common list of entities, and perform entity-linking semi-automatically: for a given entity, an annotator sees a list of entities of the same type inserted by all annotators and can select an entity ID from the list. A snapshot of the Inforex interface is in Figure 1.

In addition, Inforex keeps track of all lemmas and IDs inserted for each surface form, and inserts them automatically, so in many cases the annotator only confirms the proposed values, which speeds up the annotation process a great deal. All annotations were made by native speakers. After annotation, we performed automatic and manual consistency checks, to reduce annotation errors, especially in entity linking.

Training and test data statistics are presented in Table 1 and 2 respectively.

The testing datasets—COVID-19 and USA 2020 ELECTIONS—were released to the participants who were given circa 2 days to return up to 5 system responses. The participants did not know the topics in advance, and did not receive the annotations. The main drive behind this decision was to push participants to build a general solution for Slavic NER, rather than to optimize their models toward a particular set of names.

5 Evaluation Methodology

The NER task (exact case-insensitive matching) and Name Normalization (or “lemmatization”) were evaluated in terms of precision, recall, and F1-measure. For NER, two types of evaluations were carried out:

⁵github.com/CLARIN-PL/Inforex

	BREXIT							ASIA BIBI							NORD STREAM							RYANAIR						
	PL	CS	RU	BG	SL	UK		PL	CS	RU	BG	SL	UK		PL	CS	RU	BG	SL	UK		PL	CS	RU	BG	SL	UK	
Documents	500	284	153	600	52	50	88	89	118	101	4	6	151	161	150	130	74	40	146	163	150	87	52	63				
PER	2 650	1 108	1 308	2 515	532	242	683	570	643	583	36	39	538	570	392	335	548	78	136	161	72	147	107	33				
LOC	3 524	1 279	666	2 407	403	336	403	366	567	388	24	57	1 430	1 689	1 320	910	1 362	339	821	871	902	344	384	455				
ORG	3 080	1 039	828	2 455	301	166	286	214	419	245	10	30	837	477	792	540	460	449	529	707	500	238	408	193				
EVT	1 072	471	261	776	165	62	14	3	1	8	0	0	15	9	5	6	50	14	7	12	0	4	8	0				
PRO	668	232	137	490	31	17	55	42	49	63	2	1	405	364	510	331	243	8	114	66	82	79	101	20				
Total	10 994	4 129	3 200	8 643	1 445	823	1 441	1 195	1 679	1 287	72	127	3 225	3 116	3 020	2 122	2 664	948	1 607	1 817	1 556	812	1 008	701				
<i>Distinct</i>																												
Surface forms	2 820	1 111	783	1 200	596	234	508	303	406	412	51	87	845	770	892	504	902	336	514	475	400	323	673	187				
Lemmas	2 133	840	568	1 091	411	177	412	248	317	360	41	77	634	550	583	448	600	244	419	400	332	315	520	137				
Entity IDs	1 506	583	268	772	288	127	273	160	178	230	31	64	441	392	321	305	465	177	322	306	251	245	428	108				

Table 1: Overview of the training datasets.

	COVID-19						USA 2020 ELECTIONS					
	PL	CS	RU	BG	SL	UK	PL	CS	RU	BG	SL	UK
Documents	103	155	83	151	178	85	66	85	163	151	143	83
PER	419	478	559	351	834	215	566	447	3203	1539	2589	672
LOC	369	474	701	759	1228	364	827	277	3457	1093	1268	541
ORG	402	318	628	589	965	455	243	99	2486	557	578	384
EVT	240	393	435	465	612	269	86	63	396	170	118	257
PRO	137	155	400	168	274	143	87	56	846	240	254	124
Total	1567	1818	2723	2332	3913	1446	1810	942	10398	3599	4807	1978
<i>Distinct</i>												
Surface forms	688	941	1436	1092	2190	622	484	377	3440	1117	1605	537
Lemmas	557	745	1133	1016	1774	509	356	279	2593	1019	1129	390
Entity IDs	404	562	796	764	1400	369	278	200	1669	668	833	270

Table 2: Overview of the test datasets.

- **Relaxed:** An entity mentioned in a given document is considered to be extracted correctly if the system response includes *at least one* annotation of a named mention of this entity (regardless of whether the extracted mention is in base form);
- **Strict:** The system response should include exactly one annotation *for each* unique form of a named mention of an entity in a given document, i.e., identifying all variants of an entity is required.

In relaxed evaluation we additionally distinguish between *exact* and *partial matching*: in the latter case, an entity mentioned in a given document is considered to be extracted correctly if the system response includes at least one partial match of a named mention of this entity.

We evaluate systems at several levels of granularity: we measure performance for (a) all NE types and all languages, (b) each given NE type and all languages, (c) all NE types for each language, and (d) each given NE type per language.

In the name normalization task, we take into account only correctly recognized entity mentions and only those that were normalized (on both the annotation and system’s sides). Formally, let $N_{correct}$ denote the number of all correctly recognized entity mentions for which the system returned a correct base form. Let N_{key} denote the number of all normalized entity mentions in the gold-standard answer key and $N_{response}$ denote

the number of all normalized entity mentions in the system’s response. We define precision and recall for the name normalization task as:

$$Recall = \frac{N_{correct}}{N_{key}} \quad Precision = \frac{N_{correct}}{N_{response}}$$

In evaluating document-level, single-language and cross-lingual entity linking we adopted the Link-Based Entity-Aware metric (LEA) (Moosavi and Strube, 2016), which considers how important the entity is and how well it is resolved. LEA is defined as follows. Let $K = \{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{|K|}\}$ denote the set of key entities and $R = \{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_{|R|}\}$ the set of response entities, i.e., $k_i \in K$ ($r_i \in R$) stand for set of mentions of the same entity in the key entity set (response entity set). LEA recall and precision are then defined as follows:

$$Recall_{LEA} = \frac{\sum_{k_i \in K} (imp(k_i) \cdot res(k_i))}{\sum_{k_z \in K} imp(k_z)}$$

$$Precision_{LEA} = \frac{\sum_{r_i \in R} (imp(r_i) \cdot res(r_i))}{\sum_{r_z \in R} imp(r_z)}$$

where imp and res denote the measure of importance and the resolution score for an entity, respectively. In our setting, we define $imp(e) = \log_2 |e|$ for an entity e (in K or R), $|e|$ is the number of mentions of e —i.e., the more mentions an entity has the more important it is. To avoid biasing the importance of the more frequent entities log

is used. The resolution score of key entity k_i is computed as the fraction of correctly resolved co-reference links of k_i :

$$res(k_i) = \sum_{r_j \in R} \frac{link(k_i \cap r_j)}{link(k_i)}$$

where $link(e) = (|e| \times (|e| - 1))/2$ is the number of unique co-reference links in e . For each k_i , LEA checks all response entities to check whether they are partial matches for k_i . Analogously, the resolution score of response entity r_i is computed as the fraction of co-reference links in r_i that are extracted correctly:

$$res(r_i) = \sum_{k_j \in K} \frac{link(r_i \cap k_j)}{link(r_i)}$$

LEA brings several benefits. For example, LEA considers resolved co-reference relations instead of resolved mentions and has more discriminative power than other metrics for co-reference resolution (Moosavi and Strube, 2016).

The evaluation was carried out in “case-insensitive” mode: all named mentions in system response and test corpora were lower-cased.

6 Participant Systems

Six teams submitted descriptions of their systems as BSNLP Workshop papers. We briefly review these systems here; for complete descriptions, please see the corresponding papers. Two additional teams submitted their results with short descriptions of their systems, which appear in this section.

The **UL FRI** system, (Prelevikj and Zitnik, 2021), generated results for several settings, models and languages, although the team’s main motivation is to develop effective NER tools for Slovenian. The system uses contemporary BERT and RoBERTa multilingual pre-trained models, which include Slovene among other languages. The system was further trained on the SlavNER dataset for the NER task and used the Dedupe method for the Entity Matching task. The best performing models were pre-trained on Slovene. The results also indicate that two-step prediction of NE could be beneficial. The team made their code publicly available.

The **Priberam Labs** system, (Ferreira et al., 2021), focuses on the NER task. It uses three components: a multilingual contextual embedding

model, a character-level embedding model, and a bi-affine classifier model. The paper reports results for different multilingual contextual embedding models, which included Multilingual BERT, XLM-RoBERTa, or the Slavic BERT. For different languages the best-performing models were different, but having the same language within the large pre-trained model usually improved the results—e.g., Slavic BERT, which used additional resources for Bulgarian, Russian and Polish, also performed best for these languages. The system uses heuristics to predict and resolve spans of NEs, and in this way it is able to tag overlapping entities. The code for the system is made available.

The **TLD** system, (Viksna and Skadina, 2021), uses a staged approach. The first stage is identification of NEs in context, which is treated as a sequence labeling problem and is performed by a multilingual BERT model from Google, modified by the team. Entity linking is the second stage, which uses a list of LaBSE embeddings; matched entries need to pass a pre-defined threshold of cosine similarity with existing entries; otherwise they are added as new values to the list. The third stage is normalisation of identified entities, which is performed using models provided with Stanza.

The **L3i** system, (Cabrera-Diego et al., 2021), combines BERT models with the “Frustratingly Easy” domain adaptation algorithm. It also uses other techniques to improve system’s NER performance, such as marking and enrichment of uppercase tokens, prediction of NE boundaries with a multitask approach, prediction of masked tokens, fine-tuning the language model to the domain of the document.

The **TraSpaS** system, (Suppa and Jariabka, 2021), tests the assumption that the universal open-source NLP toolkits (such as SpaCy, Stanza or Trankit) could achieve competitive performance on the Multilingual NER task, using large pre-trained Transformer-based language models available from HuggingfaceTransformers, which have not been available in previous editions of the Shared Task. The team tests the generalizability of the models to new low-resourced domains, and to languages such as Slovene and Ukrainian.

The **UWr-VL** system, (Rychlikowski et al., 2021), utilizes large collections of unstructured and structured documents for unsupervised training of embedding of lexical units and for recog-

nizing and linking multiple real-world NEs. In particular, the team makes use of CommonCrawl news articles, Wikipedia, and its structured counterpart Wikidata as knowledge sources, to address the problem of data scarcity, building neural gazetteer via collecting different embeddings from these knowledge sources. The system further uses standard neural approaches to the NER task, with a RNN classifier, in order to determine for every input word the probability of labelling it with various beginning and end NE tags.

Two more systems generated the results for the shared task—**CTC-NER** from the Cognitive Technologies Center team, and **PAISC_wxd**:

CTC-NER is a baseline prototype of a NER component of an entity recognition system currently under development at the Cognitive Technologies Center. The system has a hybrid architecture combining rule-based and ML techniques; the ML-component is loosely related to (Antonova and Soloviev, 2013). The languages currently processed include Russian, English and Ukrainian.

PAISC_wxd uses the XLM-Roberta model, followed by BiLSTM-CRF on top. In addition, the system uses data enhancement based on machine translation.

7 Evaluation Results

Figure 3 shows the performance of the systems averaged across all languages and both test corpora. For each team that provided a solution for all six languages (7 teams except **CTC-NER**), we present the best scores (*F1*, *Precision*, and *Recall*) obtained by the team in three evaluation modes.⁶

As the plots show, the best performing model, Priberam, yields F-measure 85.7% according to the *relaxed partial* evaluation, and 79.3% according to the strict evaluation. The Priberam submission scores highest in precision — 89.4% relaxed partial, and 85.1% strict — but much lower in recall — 82.2% relaxed partial, and 74.3% strict.

Among the teams that submitted results for *cross-lingual entity linking*, only two achieved results comparable with the benchmarks achieved on the Second Challenge, and this year’s results surpass those benchmarks by a substantial margin. The best results for each team, averaged across two corpora, are shown in Table 3. These results

⁶Complete results available on the Workshop’s Web page: bsnlp.cs.helsinki.fi/final-rank-2021.pdf

Figure 3: Best average performance scores obtained by the teams on the two test data

show that this task is much more difficult than entity extraction. The best performing model, TLD, achieves F-measure 50.4%.

Note that in our setting the performance on entity linking depends on the performance on name recognition and normalization: each system had to link entities that it had extracted from documents upstream, rather than link a set of correct entities.

Tables 4 and 5 present the F1-measures separated by language, for all tasks for the COVID-19 and USA 2020 ELECTIONS data sets. These tables show only the top-performing model for each team. For recognition, we show only the *relaxed* evaluation, since the results obtained on the three evaluation schemes are correlated, as can be seen from Figure 3.

The tables indicate some variation in scores obtained on the test corpora. This variation could be

COVID-19		USA 2020 ELECTIONS	
System	F1	System	F1
TLD	47.5	TLD	52.0
UWr-VL	32.8	UWr-VL	27.9
Priberam	5.8	Priberam	8.0
L3i	4.4	TraSpaS	7.9
PAISC	2.8	L3i	7.3
TraSpaS	2.7	PAISC	6.2
UL FRI	1.9	CTC-NER	2.9
CTC-NER	1.2	UL FRI	0.4

Table 3: Cross-lingual entity linking.

due to a number of factors, including actual differences in the test data, as well as differences in annotation across languages. This variation should and will be investigated in greater depth.

In Table 6 we present the results of the evaluation by entity type. As seen in the table, performance was higher overall for LOC and PER, and substantially lower for ORG and PRO, which corresponds with our findings from the previous editions of the shared task, where ORG and MISC were the most problematic categories (Piskorski et al., 2017). The PRO category also exhibits higher variance across languages and corpora than other categories, which might point to possible annotation artefacts. The results for the EVT category are less informative, since the task heavily depends on detecting the repeated central events of the corpora.

8 Conclusion

This paper reports on the 3rd Multilingual Named Entity Challenge focusing on recognizing mentions of NEs in Web documents in six Slavic languages, normalization of the NEs, and cross-lingual entity linking. The Challenge has attracted substantial interest, following the prior Challenges in 2017 and 2019, with 10 teams registering for the competition and eight teams submitting results from working systems, with multiple variants. Most systems use state-of-the-art neural network models. Overall, the results of the best-performing systems are quite strong for extraction and normalization, while cross-lingual linking is the most challenging of the tasks.

We show summary results for the main aspects of the challenge and the best-performing model for each team. For detailed, in-depth evaluations of all participating systems and their performance please consult the Shared Task’s Web page and the papers

by the respective teams.

To stimulate further research into NLP for Slavic languages, including cross-lingual entity linking, our training and test datasets, the detailed annotations, and scripts used for evaluations are made available to the public on the Shared Task’s Web page.⁷ The annotation interface is released by the Inforex team, to support further annotation of additional data for future tests.

This challenge covered six Slavic languages. For future editions of the Challenge, we plan to expand the data sets, covering a wider range of entity types, and supporting cross-lingual entity linking. We plan to expand the training and test data to include *non-Slavic* languages. We will also undertake further refinement of the underlying annotation guidelines—a highly complex task in a real-world setting. More complex phenomena also need to be addressed, e.g., coordinated NEs, contracted versions of multiple NEs, etc.

We believe that the reported results and the annotated datasets will help stimulate further research on robust, end-to-end analysis of real-world texts in Slavic languages.

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⁷bsnlp.cs.helsinki.fi/shared_task.html

COVID-19		Language											
Phase	Metric	bg	cs	pl	ru	sl	uk						
Recognition	Relaxed Partial	Priberam	83.2	UWr-VL	86.7	Priberam	87.8	L3i	76.0	UWr-VL	87.6	UWr-VL	84.8
		L3i	82.8	Priberam	86.3	UWr-VL	86.9	Priberam	75.1	Priberam	87.5	L3i	80.6
		TLD	82.2	TLD	84.1	TLD	86.4	PAISC	74.4	L3i	85.6	TLD	80.1
		UL FRI	81.6	L3i	83.9	L3i	85.0	TLD	72.9	TLD	84.2	Priberam	79.9
		UWr-VL	81.2	TraSpaS	82.0	UL FRI	83.4	UL FRI	71.9	TraSpaS	83.9	PAISC	78.3
		TraSpaS	80.9	UL FRI	80.4	TraSpaS	82.5	TraSpaS	70.2	PAISC	80.1	UL FRI	78.3
		PAISC	79.7	PAISC	77.6	PAISC	81.0	CTC-NER	69.3	UL FRI	79.1	TraSpaS	78.1
								UWr-VL	67.1			CTC-NER	65.0
Normalization		UWr-VL	33.3	TraSpaS	47.0	UWr-VL	57.4	CTC-NER	40.4	UWr-VL	53.0	TraSpaS	53.7
		UL FRI	21.4	TLD	45.2	UL FRI	47.2	UL FRI	39.9	UL FRI	40.5	UWr-VL	51.5
		TLD	13.8	UWr-VL	44.8	TraSpaS	46.2	TraSpaS	38.6	TraSpaS	34.3	UL FRI	50.7
		TraSpaS	10.0	UL FRI	44.4	TLD	45.3	TLD	36.2	TLD	32.3	TLD	46.3
		Priberam	0.0	Priberam	0.0	Priberam	0.0	UWr-VL	27.2	Priberam	0.0	CTC-NER	39.2
		L3i	0.0	L3i	0.0	L3i	0.0	Priberam	0.0	L3i	0.0	Priberam	0.0
		PAISC	0.0	PAISC	0.0	PAISC	0.0	L3i	0.0	PAISC	0.0	L3i	0.0
								PAISC	0.0			PAISC	0.0
Entity linking	Document level	UWr-VL	37.6	TLD	47.0	UWr-VL	61.2	TLD	42.5	UWr-VL	52.0	TLD	48.9
		TLD	24.6	UWr-VL	46.0	TLD	44.7	UWr-VL	30.5	TLD	45.2	UWr-VL	45.3
		L3i	13.3	UL FRI	29.8	UL FRI	26.4	UL FRI	20.4	UL FRI	29.6	UL FRI	24.7
		Priberam	12.4	Priberam	23.9	PAISC	20.4	Priberam	15.5	Priberam	16.8	Priberam	23.7
		TraSpaS	11.5	L3i	22.5	L3i	20.3	PAISC	13.8	L3i	15.6	L3i	22.3
		PAISC	11.4	TraSpaS	22.1	Priberam	20.0	L3i	13.3	TraSpaS	14.9	TraSpaS	22.0
		UL FRI	6.1	PAISC	21.2	TraSpaS	18.4	TraSpaS	12.2	PAISC	13.8	PAISC	17.8
								CTC-NER	3.5			CTC-NER	2.3
	Single language	UWr-VL	67.9	TLD	66.5	UWr-VL	73.0	TLD	47.4	UWr-VL	66.4	TLD	61.7
		TLD	57.1	UWr-VL	66.1	TLD	67.8	UWr-VL	38.9	TLD	59.2	UWr-VL	61.5
		PAISC	16.4	UL FRI	40.2	UL FRI	38.8	UL FRI	20.1	UL FRI	32.7	UL FRI	36.8
		L3i	10.9	PAISC	15.9	PAISC	13.7	Priberam	6.2	TraSpaS	10.0	Priberam	15.9
		Priberam	8.7	L3i	11.2	Priberam	9.3	L3i	4.2	Priberam	7.2	L3i	7.7
		UL FRI	7.6	TraSpaS	11.2	TraSpaS	8.2	PAISC	3.5	L3i	4.2	PAISC	7.5
		TraSpaS	3.6	Priberam	8.0	L3i	7.9	TraSpaS	2.0	PAISC	1.8	TraSpaS	6.3
								CTC-NER	1.8			CTC-NER	2.6

Table 4: F1-measure results for the COVID-19 corpus.

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USA 2020 ELECTIONS		Language											
Phase	Metric	bg	cs	pl	ru	sl	uk						
Recognition	Relaxed Partial	L3i	89.8	UWr-VL	91.3	Priberam	92.3	L3i	83.7	Priberam	91.5	TLD	84.6
		Priberam	88.7	Priberam	90.7	L3i	92.0	Priberam	83.4	L3i	91.5	Priberam	84.6
		TraSpaS	88.1	L3i	90.2	TLD	90.8	TraSpaS	81.5	UWr-VL	90.4	L3i	84.5
		UWr-VL	87.3	TLD	88.5	UWr-VL	89.8	TLD	80.9	TLD	89.8	TraSpaS	83.3
		TLD	87.3	UL FRI	88.4	TraSpaS	89.2	UL FRI	80.5	TraSpaS	89.4	UWr-VL	83.3
		UL FRI	86.9	TraSpaS	87.8	UL FRI	89.1	UWr-VL	77.2	UL FRI	88.6	UL FRI	83.2
		PAISC	83.6	PAISC	82.6	PAISC	66.4	PAISC	77.1	PAISC	86.0	PAISC	77.0
								CTC-NER	75.4			CTC-NER	71.1
Normalization		UWr-VL	51.3	UWr-VL	51.9	UWr-VL	62.1	TraSpaS	50.7	UWr-VL	62.4	UL FRI	56.9
		UL FRI	21.9	TraSpaS	42.0	TLD	51.0	UL FRI	48.8	UL FRI	43.9	TraSpaS	56.8
		TLD	19.1	TLD	40.1	UL FRI	50.1	TLD	46.5	TraSpaS	34.2	TLD	55.3
		TraSpaS	17.9	UL FRI	39.7	TraSpaS	42.4	CTC-NER	44.8	TLD	31.9	CTC-NER	36.9
		Priberam	0.0	Priberam	0.0	Priberam	0.0	UWr-VL	25.6	Priberam	0.0	UWr-VL	26.5
		L3i	0.0	L3i	0.0	L3i	0.0	Priberam	0.0	L3i	0.0	Priberam	0.0
		PAISC	0.0	PAISC	0.0	PAISC	0.0	L3i	0.0	PAISC	0.0	L3i	0.0
								PAISC	0.0			PAISC	0.0
Entity linking	Document level	UWr-VL	63.7	UWr-VL	64.3	UWr-VL	67.1	TLD	44.8	UWr-VL	67.3	UWr-VL	58.9
		TLD	58.7	TLD	55.3	TLD	62.3	UWr-VL	35.8	TLD	59.3	TLD	52.2
		Priberam	12.5	UL FRI	37.5	UL FRI	44.9	UL FRI	32.2	UL FRI	43.3	UL FRI	28.8
		L3i	12.1	L3i	30.5	Priberam	18.2	Priberam	12.3	L3i	18.3	Priberam	25.4
		TraSpaS	11.7	Priberam	29.5	L3i	18.0	L3i	12.3	Priberam	17.9	L3i	23.9
		PAISC	11.4	TraSpaS	28.6	TraSpaS	17.4	PAISC	9.9	TraSpaS	17.1	TraSpaS	23.5
		UL FRI	4.5	PAISC	21.6	PAISC	13.4	TraSpaS	9.8	PAISC	15.8	PAISC	16.8
								CTC-NER	2.8			CTC-NER	1.5
	Single language	UWr-VL	68.5	TLD	69.0	TLD	74.9	TLD	50.1	TLD	68.7	TLD	62.2
		TLD	67.1	UWr-VL	66.0	UWr-VL	69.9	UWr-VL	39.3	UWr-VL	66.5	UWr-VL	52.9
		PAISC	12.8	UL FRI	50.0	UL FRI	37.7	UL FRI	13.6	UL FRI	21.3	UL FRI	23.0
		Priberam	10.1	L3i	18.1	Priberam	14.8	Priberam	5.6	Priberam	8.4	TraSpaS	21.4
		TraSpaS	8.6	Priberam	17.7	L3i	14.5	L3i	5.5	L3i	8.3	L3i	20.5
		L3i	8.6	TraSpaS	17.7	TraSpaS	13.4	TraSpaS	5.1	TraSpaS	8.2	Priberam	20.2
		UL FRI	8.3	PAISC	14.1	PAISC	10.7	PAISC	4.4	PAISC	7.2	PAISC	12.9
									CTC-NER	3.6		CTC-NER	9.4

Table 5: Evaluation results (F1-measure) for the USA 2020 ELECTION corpus.

	COVID-19						USA 2020 ELECTIONS					
	bg	cs	pl	ru	sl	uk	bg	cs	pl	ru	sl	uk
Per	98.0	98.1	98.3	83.1	98.2	96.6	93.6	97.4	94.2	93.1	96.3	98.7
Loc	95.8	96.4	96.7	95.1	95.7	97.3	97.5	96.9	97.6	93.1	98.2	93.8
Org	86.5	89.4	91.3	82.9	88.8	87.6	86.6	89.6	86.3	76.6	76.7	81.7
Pro	55.1	76.2	75.6	47.6	63.4	49.4	80.7	87.4	90.2	66.9	77.7	69.9
Evt	52.6	40.1	57.8	52.6	63.5	75.9	29.6	26.1	40.5	55.7	38.0	16.1

Table 6: Recognition F1-measure (relaxed partial) by entity type—best-performing systems for each language.

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